

Suitability of Water Catchment Areas and Their Implications for the Development of Balikpapan City

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Abstract:

Balikpapan City, one of the National Activity Centers, has advantages in terms of geostatistics. It is predicted that it will continue to develop into a big city, which is in line with the determination of the National Capital City location in Penajam Paser Utara. However, along with these developments, there are challenges in balancing space utilisation where protected areas are increasingly threatened, including the catchment function zone. Water catchment areas have one of the important functions as a place for rainwater to seep into the soil and subsequently become groundwater, so their existence has an important role in efforts to prevent the danger of

flooding and land subsidence. Therefore, this study aims to analyse the potential of water catchment areas and their implications for developing Balikpapan City. The method combines historical literature research with analysis of the Geographic Information System (GIS) of Balikpapan City. The techniques used include multi-criteria analysis and analysis of the suitability of spatial pattern plan, the last stage of formulating spatial recommendations that need to be carried out in anticipating negative impacts due to future city development. In conclusion, it was concluded that Balikpapan City has 33% (16,950 ha) of the high water catchment potential area, divided into five typologies of suitability of water catchment potential, between very suitable and inappropriate. Based on the Regulation of the Mayor of Balikpapan Number 22 of 2021 concerning spatial pattern plan, 61% of the areas with High Water Infiltration Potential are designated areas with a protection function. Meanwhile, 39% of the other High Water Infiltration Potential areas are in regions with cultivation functions.

Keywords: *Water catchment area, Geographic Information System (GIS), Multi-criteria analysis, Balikpapan City.*

Introduction

As a rapidly growing city in East Kalimantan, Balikpapan faces the challenge of effectively managing its land use and water resources. The development of an urban area will impact the increasing need for space to accommodate

various activities that result in land conversion, environmental damage and decreased ecological carrying capacity. The city's proximity to the Makassar Strait makes it particularly vulnerable to changes in coastline and potential environmental degradation (Camila & Saraswati, 2020).

Balikpapan City is one of the urban areas affected by the National Capital City (IKN) designation based on the Ministry of National Development Planning/ National Development Planning Agency (Bappenas). Data quoted from *mediaindonesia.com* (March 12, 2022), the number of people in the IKN will increase by 1.9 million people, occupying an area of 256 thousand hectares, as well as the surrounding cities of Balikpapan and Samarinda are predicted to reach 4.5-5 million people. This is a warning of the increasing need for cultivated land (including housing, trade and services, offices, and industry) that is needed. Ideally, a city has an ecological function to support city life to be more livable. The rapid population growth in Balikpapan has led to a high demand for land for housing, which has resulted in changes in land function. (Marselina, Nurhayati, & Pandia, 2022).

Water catchment areas play an essential role in maintaining the urban environment to maintain the stability of the groundwater and surface water cycles and as an area that is maintained to prevent natural disasters such as floods (Caja et al., 2018). Recharge areas, which serve as natural repositories that collect and store surface water and groundwater, are critical for replenishing aquifers and water supplies (Megdal, Dillon, & Seasholes, 2014). However, expanding urban areas and infrastructure development can often lead to the loss of these critical water catchment areas (HIBBS & SHARP JR, 2012).

The dynamics of urban development towards open land occupancy can undoubtedly cause the loss of water catchment areas, including those found in the Bogor Area (Irsan et al., 2021), the Brantas River Basin Sub-basin (Harisuseno & Andawayanti, U., Suhartanto, E., Anggara, W.W.S., Oktavianto, S.D.H., 2013), Manado City (Seng, Kumurur, & Moniaga, 2015), as well as in South India (Seng et al., 2015), but in urban areas that are in coastal regions the environmental impact will be felt greater because it is located downstream, especially when there is a high tide. Similar trends have been observed in Samarinda City, the capital of East Kalimantan province, where rapid urban development has led to a concerning reduction

in the land's ability to absorb water. (Warsilan, 2019). The suitability of water catchment areas in Balikpapan City is crucial for the city's future development. Ideally, a city has an ecological function to support city life to be more livable. Each municipality must meet the need for open space to support the urban ecosystem by developing a water catchment area that balances urban development and environmental sustainability. Therefore, this research is essential to identify potential locations for developing water catchment areas, which are then compared with the space utilization plan set out in the City of Balikpapan so that it can be an input on land use policies, especially in high water catchment areas.

Materials and Methods

This research was carried out by taking the following steps:

1. Conduct a literature study to determine the parameters and criteria of the Water Catchment Area.
2. Weighting parameters, criteria, and classifications are used to determine the delineation of water catchment areas.
3. Conduct a final criteria analysis and overlap analysis.
4. Conducting an analysis of the Suitability of the Water Catchment Area Delineation Map with a Map of Protected Areas Spatial Pattern Plan.
5. Develop spatial recommendations.

The research location is Balikpapan City, East Kalimantan Province, Indonesia (Figure 1). This study uses two data collection methods, namely secondary data collection and primary data collection. Secondary data collection aims to find information from literature studies and related agencies regarding planning documents, map documents, and spatial satellite imagery. Primary data collection is from groundwater level observation and ground check results of water catchment area suitability analysis.

To obtain a representative water catchment area delineation, referring to literature reviewed previously and considering the availability and ease of access to data, 8 (eight) parameters can

be used for analysis purposes (Table 1), namely topographic elevation, slope, vegetation density, land cover, soil cover texture, rock permeability, groundwater level position, and rainfall.

Figure 1. Research Location

Table 1. Parameters, Criteria, and Classification to Determine the Delineation of Water Catchment Areas

Parameter	Criteria Assumptions	Spatial Classification	Number
Slope*	Land with a sloping slope permeates more water than steep land.	<5%	5
		5-20%	4
		20-40%	3
		40-60%	2
		>60%	1
Topographic elevation [‡]	Areas at high altitudes are relatively more permeable to water than those at low altitudes.	>80 m	5
		60-80 m	4
		40-60 m	3
		20-40 m	2
		0-20 m	1
Land cover*	Built-up areas absorb less water than natural areas overgrown with trees.	Forest	5
		bushes	4
		bushes	3
		Rice Fields-	2
		Settlements	1
Vegetation density	Areas with dense vegetation have higher permeability than areas with sparse vegetation.	> 0,45	5
		0,33 – 0,45	4

(NDVI) ‡		0,25 – 0,33	3
		0,11 – 0,25	2
		0 – 0,11	1
Soil texture*	Soils with more sand texture permeates water compared to clay-textured soil.	Sand	5
		Loamy sand	4
		Sandy loam	3
		Fine sandy loam	2
		Clay	1
Rock permeability †	The higher the permeability rate, the easier it is for a rock to permeate water.	> 10 ³ m/day	5
		10 ¹ - 10 ³ m/ day	4
		10 ⁻² - 10 ¹ m/ day	3
		10 ⁻⁴ - 10 ⁻² m/	2
		< 10 ⁻⁴ m/ day	1
Groundwater table position ^ †	Deep groundwater table relatively permeates more water from shallow groundwater surface.	> 30 m bmt	5
		20 – 30 m bmt	4
		20 – 10 m bmt	3
		10 – 5 m bmt	2
		< 5 m bmt	1
Rainfall*	The higher the rainfall, the greater the water infiltration rate.	>3000 mm/yr	5
		2000-3000 mm/	4
		1000-2000 mm/	3
		500-1000 mm/ yr	2
		<500 mm/ yr	1

Source: *(Kementerian Pekerjaan Umum, 2013); ‡ (Geologi, Pusat Lingkungan, 2007); ^ (Kementerian Energi dan Sumber Daya Mineral, 2018); † (Sari, Gun, & Hudman, 2005)

The method used in parameter weighting combines the ranking method and the tug-of-war analysis method. First, all parameters (i) are sorted based on their degree/percentage of importance (p) in the formation of water catchment areas. Furthermore, the rating value is normalized into the range of 0 - 1. The

normalization process produces a weight for each parameter that adds up to 1.

$$w_i = \frac{p_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n p_i} \quad (1)$$

Table 2. Parameter Weighting Refers to Several Similar Studies that have Been Conducted Before

Num of Referensi	Parameter								Sum
	S	T	Lc	Dv	St	Rp	Gt	R	
Maghribi & Supriatna, 2020	0,11	-	0,09	-	0,25	-	-	0,05	0,50
Danaryanto & Sudadi, 2007	0,27	-	-	-	0,20	0,07	0,33	0,13	1,00
Triadi Putranto & Eko Aryanto, 2018	0,10	-	0,18	-	0,14	0,29	0,05	0,24	1,00
Rajasekhar, Ajaykumar, Raju G, & Bhagat, 2021	0,11	-	0,13	-	0,09	0,08	0,20	0,18	0,79
Abijith et al., 2020	0,10	-	0,18	-	0,07	0,14	-	0,04	0,53

Irsan et al., 2021	0,19	-	0,14	-	0,09	0,29	-	-	0,71
Total	0,88	0,00	0,72	0,00	0,84	0,87	0,58	0,64	4,53
Avg	0,15	0,00	0,14	0,00	0,14	0,17	0,19	0,13	0,926
Weight	0,16	0,03	0,10	0,05	0,15	0,18	0,20	0,13	1,000

Note: S – Slope; T – Topographic; Lc - Land Cover; St - Soil Texture; Rp - Rock permeability; Gt - Groundwater table; R – Rainfall.

Overlap Analysis

Pouring information into thematic maps, where one parameter represents one thematic map (layer). Then, an overlay process is carried out on all layers to produce a suitability value using the following formula:

$$SWI = 0,16. x_S + 0,03. x_T + 0,10. x_{Lc} + 0,05. x_{Dv} + 0,15. x_{St} + 0,18. x_{Rp} + 0,20. x_{Gt} + 0,13. x_R \quad (2)$$

(*SWI*) Suitability of water infiltration as a value of suitability for water infiltration. (*X*) attribute

numbers for the class of each parameter. Process of delineation of water catchment areas (see Figure 2).

Analysis of the Suitability of the Water Catchment Area Delineation Map with a Map of Protected Areas Spatial Pattern Plan

The analysis method used is a spatial multi-criteria evaluation, but with the Boolean overlay technique approach, where the output is in the form of information appropriate or inappropriate. The results of this analysis are a reference for follow-up recommendations (see Figure 3).

Figure 2. The Process of Delineation of Water Catchment Areas

Figure 3. The process Suitability of the Catchment Area Delineation Protected Areas Spatial Pattern Plan

Results

Physical-Environmental Hue of the Region

Balikpapan City, as a coastal city, has the characteristics of a sloping slope, around 36% of the area of 18,443.33 Ha at a hill of <2%. The gentle slope allows rainwater to penetrate better into the soil, so rainwater can seep into and enrich the soil layer underneath. However, the city's ongoing development and expansion have reduced soil infiltration capability, increasing surface runoff and a lower groundwater recharge rate (Konrad, 2003) (Juwita & Santoso, 2019).

Soil Type Hapludults Paleudults is the most dominant soil type at around 73%, has a positive impact on water catchment areas, and has an essential role in providing groundwater and maintaining ecosystem sustainability. The water absorption ability of Hapludults varies depending on their physical and chemical conditions (Maliva, 2020). Hapludults generally have good water absorption because their pore structure allows water to permeate efficiently.

As well as rock permeability data, groundwater level position data also refers to the Groundwater Potential Map (Geological Agency - Center for Groundwater and Environmental

Geology, 2005). We made observations of the groundwater level position at several points spread across almost all corners of the Balikpapan City area (Figure 5). Groundwater levels and catchment areas are interrelated. The catchment area will be more comprehensive if the groundwater level is low because rainwater will seep into the soil more easily. On the other hand, if the groundwater level is high, the catchment area will be more limited because the soil is already saturated with water and cannot accommodate more.

Potential Water Catchment Area

Based on the overlay analysis of the seven parameters determined, the delineation of water catchment areas of Balikpapan City was produced (see Figure 2). Nearly 17,000 hectares of Balikpapan City is a Water Catchment Area (WCA) with a High Potential class category. This area equals about 33% of the city's total area. West Balikpapan District has the most significant WCA potential, with an area of 12,828 hectares, followed by East Balikpapan District (3,045 hectares). Meanwhile, the area with the slightest WCA potential is Balikpapan Kota District (0,03 hectares) (see Figure 6). Likewise with the results of the analysis (Juwita

& Santoso, 2019), areas that have the potential to be rainwater catchment areas are seen from regions with as many as 10 locations from 15 locations, with the potential as a catchment area is around 60% of all research locations.

Figure 4. Thematic Maps Parameter of Delineation Water Catchment Areas

Figure 5. Observation of the Position of Groundwater Level

Meanwhile, the rapid conversion of green open spaces into built-up areas, coupled with the expansion of impervious surfaces, has significantly diminished the infiltration rates and overall water absorption capacities of the soils in Balikpapan City (Gunawan, Hassan, Razali, & Cahyono, 2021).

Figure 6. Potential Water Catchment Area Maps

Suitability with Balikpapan Spatial Plans

The suitability analysis in this research is to determine the designation of water catchment zones that have been planned in the Balikpapan City Spatial Plan in accordance with the potential of the water catchment area. Based on the results of the analysis, it's known that of the 762.53 hectares of Water Catchment Zones stipulated in the 2021-2041 Balikpapan City RDTR (Detail Spatial Plans, an area of 23.72 hectares or 3% of them are adjacent to Non-Potential regions so they are categorized as Non-Conform. Meanwhile, 315 hectares, or 41%, are in areas with high water infiltration potential, so they are classified as Suitable. The rest (423 hectares or 56%) are in the Medium potential area, so it can generally be categorized as Quite Suitable.

Figure 7. Map of Suitability of Water Infiltration Potential with Water Infiltration Zone Plan

Discussion

The characteristics of Balikpapan City based on the physical-environmental parameters of the water catchment area, describe conditions that are quite potential as groundwater recharge areas. However, along with the development of land use, some potential locations for water catchment areas have actually turned into pavements. The current problem is that the city of Balikpapan has become a center of activity that continues to grow along with the relocation of the State Capital from Jakarta to Paser Penajam Utara (East Kalimantan). Regarding the population issues and the government's planning for the new capital city of Indonesia, Balikpapan will be a buffer city facing serious risk in water supply issues in the future (Mamangkey, Sukmara, & Ariyaningsih, 2021), the threat of natural disaster risks such as floods, rob floods, extreme weather (Caja et al., 2018).

The activities planned on the 2041 spatial plan map are still quite in accordance with areas that have high potential to become water catchment areas (Table 2). However, for the area that no longer has a function as a water catchment covering an area of 2,590.2 hectares where most of the land has been developed into settlements and urban utilities.

To respond to the development of a balanced city, in line with the determination of the State Capital in Paser Penajam Utara (Nusantara), Balikpapan City must address the burden it faces as a transportation and trade hub in East Kalimantan Province. This includes avoiding development in water catchment areas, carefully selecting only urgent buildings to be constructed in those areas, applying disincentives for development, and participating in environmental improvement programs. Additionally, the government should designate well-preserved areas as ownership assets to optimize the ecological function and support the carrying capacity of Balikpapan City.

Table 2. Typology of Suitability Between the Potential of High Category Water Infiltration and the Spatial Plan

Typology	Suitability	Spatial Plan 2021-2041	Area (Ha)	Distribution of Districts	Recommendations
Typology 1	Suitable	Magrove Ecosystems, Protected Forests, Permanent Production Forests, Urban Forests, Wildlife Reserves, Urban Parks	12,348.39	All Districts	Optimizing Regional Functions According to Spatial Plans
Typology 2	Accordance	Around Lakes or Reservoirs, Coastal Boundaries, River Boundaries	137.20	Districts : Balikpapan Barat, Balikpapan Selatan, Balikpapan Timur, Balikpapan Utara	Utilization of protection functions for the development of forest plants
Typology 3	Quite Suitable	Plantations, Food Crops	1,144.97	District Balikpapan Timur	Integrated agricultural development with forest plants according to the concept of Agroforestry.
Typology 4	Potential Suitable	Nature Tourism	41.80	District Balikpapan Timur	Selective Development of Tourism Activities
Typology 5	Not Suitable	Aquaculture Fisheries, Office, Security Defense, Mixed, Animal Husbandry, High Density Houses, Medium Density Houses, Low Density Houses, Fuel Stations, Industrial Centers, Transportation	2,547.06	All Districts	Determination of Provisions for the Development of Built Land Equipped with Infiltration Wells (Zero Run Off).
Typology 6	Very inappropriate	Landfill	1.34	District Balikpapan Timur	Environmentally friendly Landfill Development
Typology 7	As a Water Catchment Area in Spatial Planning (RDTR)	Water Infiltration	315.08	District Balikpapan Timur, District Balikpapan Barat	Determination as a Protected Area (Rimba Kota) or Developed Land Development through the Zero Run Off Concept

Conclusion

The suitability and preservation of water catchment areas in Balikpapan City is crucial for its future development and environmental sustainability. While Balikpapan's natural characteristics, such as its gentle slopes, provide opportunities for effective water absorption and groundwater recharge, the city's rapid and unchecked urbanization has significantly

diminished this vital capacity. To maintain a balanced and sustainable development trajectory, Balikpapan City must prioritize the comprehensive preservation of its remaining water catchment areas. This includes carefully regulating any development within these critical zones, enforcing strict land use policies, and actively participating in robust environmental improvement and restoration programs. By safeguarding its natural water absorption and

storage capabilities, Balikpapan can better prepare for the challenges of population growth, water scarcity, and climate change impacts, ensuring a more livable and resilient future for the city and its residents.

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